

Compounds of Aluminium with Nitrogen Containing Organic Ligands, Part I

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The reactions of anhydrous aluminium chloride with sodium salt of phthalimide, succinimide and benzimide in different stoichiometric ratios have been studied in non-aqueous media. Three types of derivatives viz. $AlCl_3(lig)$, $AlCl(lig)_2$ and $Al(lig)_3$ (where lig = ligand i.e. phthalimide, succinimide and benzimide anion) have been isolated in almost quantitative yields. These derivatives are either light yellow or white solids with high melting points. The identity of these compounds has been established with the help of elemental analyses, molecular weight determinations, and I.R. spectra.

A number of aluminium compounds containing oxygen donor organic ligands have been extensively studied by Mehrotra et. al.¹⁻⁵ and Urbain⁶ but only a few references on aluminium compounds containing nitrogen donor ligands⁷⁻⁹ are available in literature. In an earlier investigation we have studied the reactions of Schiff's bases with anhydrous aluminium chloride in non-aqueous media¹⁰. It was thought worthwhile to undertake a detailed study of the reactions of anhydrous aluminium chloride with some other potential nitrogen containing organic ligands.

Experimental

Anhydrous aluminium chloride was obtained by subliming Riedel-grade sample and its composition and purity was ascertained by analysis (Found: Al, 20.36; Cl, 79.6%; requires: Al, 20.29; Cl, 79.7%) Ethanol was refluxed over sodium metal and finally dried azeotropically with small quantity of dry benzene.

The reactions were carried out in all glass appa-

ratus fitted with standard interchangeable joints (quick-fit) and moisture was excluded from all the experiments. Aluminium was determined gravimetrically (by dissolving the compound in hydrochloric acid and precipitating and weighing) as oxinate. The percentage of aluminium was further confirmed by igniting the oxinate and weighing as oxide. Chloride was estimated as silver chloride gravimetrically. Nitrogen was determined by Klett-Summerson's photoelectric colorimeter using filter No. 43. Molecular weights were measured ebullioscopically in dry ethanol by elevation of boiling point method.

The reactions of anhydrous aluminium chloride with sodium phthalimide in molar ratios 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3.

The reactions of $AlCl_3$ with sodium phthalimide and other ligands were carried out in dry ethanol using the following general procedure. Stoichiometric quantity of aluminium chloride was dissolved in moisture free ethanol and required quantity of sodium phthalimide was also dissolved in a separate

TABLE

S. No.	Name and Formulae of the compounds	Mol. wt.	ANALYSES						Mol. wt.
			Found Al%	Found N%	Cl%	Calculated Al%	Calculated N%	Calculated Cl%	
1.	Dichloro aluminium monophthalimide $AlCl_2(C_8H_4O_2N)$	215.3	12.72	4.5	30.01	11.06	5.7	29.09	244
2.	Monochloro aluminium Bis-phthalimide $AlCl(C_8H_4O_2N)_2$	235	8.21	7.7	11.81	7.60	7.9	10.02	254.5
3.	Aluminium Tris-phthalimide $Al(C_8H_4O_2N)_3$	—	5.92	6.3	0.007	5.50	8.6	0.0	—
4.	Dichloro aluminium monosuccinimide $AlCl_2(C_4H_4O_2N)$	188	14.02	8.4	36.14	13.77	7.1	36.75	196
5.	Monochloro aluminium Bis-succinimide $AlCl(C_4H_4O_2N)_2$	—	11.08	12.0	13.92	10.46	10.8	13.75	—
6.	Aluminium Tris-succinimide $Al(C_4H_4O_2N)_3$	—	9.12	13.5	0.005	8.4	13.08	0.0	—
7.	Dichloro aluminium mono benzimide $AlCl_2(C_{14}H_{10}O_2N)$	335	8.22	10.4	22.02	8.01	8.6	21.06	322
8.	Monochloro aluminium Bis-benzimide $AlCl(C_{14}H_{10}O_2N)_2$	—	5.09	10.0	6.72	4.99	10.3	6.56	—
9.	Aluminium Tris-benzimide $Al(C_{14}H_{10}O_2N)_3$	—	4.05	10.4	0.006	3.62	10.1	0.0	—

flask by heating over an oil bath (110°-115°) for 15-30 min. Aluminium chloride solution was slowly transferred to ligand solution through a bent tube fitted with B₂₄ cones and a side calcium chloride tube. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 7-11 hr at 110°-115° bath temperature. Sodium chloride slowly settled at the bottom of the flask and was removed by filtration through a quick-fit filtering apparatus. The excess of solvent was removed by distillation and the product was dried at room temperature (30°/0.01 mm.) to afford white or yellowish powder soluble in ethanol.

The characteristics and analytical results of all the aluminium derivatives prepared during this investigation have been summarised in the table.

Results and Discussion

A large number of complexes of imides with almost all alkali metals¹¹, transition metals like copper¹², nickel¹², cobalt¹³ and gold¹⁴, and double complexes of copper-barium and mercury-potassium have been reported in literature. Succinimide forms addition compounds with titanium tetrachloride¹⁵. But a survey of the available literature revealed that imide derivatives of aluminium and boron have not been investigated at all. In view of this and the acidic character of N-hydrogen, a study of the reactions of anhydrous aluminium chloride with simple imides like succinimide, benzimide and phthalimide in different stoichiometric ratios were initially started in non-aqueous medium. Evolution of hydrogen chloride ensued immediately after refluxing had started and even after continuous heating for several hours, the evolution did not cease. Preliminary analysis of aluminium and chloride contents in the products revealed the incompleteness of the reactions and the sluggish nature could be attributed to feeble acidic character of N-hydrogen.

Thus sodium salts of the imides instead of imides as such were used. They were obtained by heating a mixture of alcoholic solution of an imide with sodium ethoxide in dry ethanol¹⁶. The sodium salts of the imides (succinimide, benzimide and phthalimide) are insoluble in cold dry ethanol but are fairly soluble in hot-solvent. The products obtained after completion of the reactions and processing of the reaction mixture were analysed for aluminium chloride and nitrogen contents and were found to correspond to mono-, di- and tri-imide derivatives of aluminium. All the reactions can precisely be represented as follows :—

Molecular weight determinations in dry ethanol show that the compounds are monomeric.

The phthalimide derivatives of aluminium are yellowish powdery substances while those of succinimide and benzimide are white powders. All of them are insoluble in benzene, chloroform and petroleum ether (40°-60°) but dissolve in moisture free ethanol. They do not melt upto 250° (high melting solids) and remain undecomposed.

Infrared spectra

The infrared spectra of these compounds have been recorded (4000-650 cm⁻¹) with Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer using KBr optics. Characteristic C=O absorption bands appear at 1667 cm⁻¹, 1775 cm⁻¹ and 1665 cm⁻¹ in sodium phthalimide, sodium succinimide and sodium benzimide respectively and in derivatives they occur at 1792 cm⁻¹ to 1640 cm⁻¹.

Imide group in general possesses a formal plane of symmetry and so two frequencies are expected characteristic of two carbonyl groups corresponding to symmetric and antisymmetric vibrations of the two carbonyl functions in phase and out of phase. Peaks at 1775 cm⁻¹ and 1718 cm⁻¹ might be attributed to such stretching in the ligand. In the derivatives they appear at 1790 cm⁻¹ and 1720 cm⁻¹ and a little shifting is probably due to the presence of N-substituent (attachment of aluminium atom). The mechanical coupling is very effective in imides¹⁷ and it is due to this that carbonyl stretching frequencies are considerably sensitive to the degree of conjugation between imide group and N-substituent. In aluminium derivatives, therefore, the shifting might be occurring due to probable coordination through nitrogen and carbonyl donors. C-N-C bending vibrations may be assigned to peak at 1410 cm⁻¹ in ligands and at 1420 cm⁻¹ in the derivatives. A peak of medium intensity appears in the compounds at 1470 cm⁻¹ and no assignment appears to be possible at the moment.

The Al-N-vibration occurs in the far infrared regions falling between (411-391 cm⁻¹) and so the reported spectroscopic observations do not throw any light on this linkage. Similarly Al-Cl vibrations are found in the region (339-200 cm⁻¹) and no assignment is possible for those bands also.

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